

New biologically active flavonol glycoside from *Cassia sophera* Linn.

R. N. Yadava* and Parul Jain

Natural Products Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract : A new biologically active flavonol glycoside **1**, m.p. 282–284 °C, m.f. C₃₃H₄₀O₁₉, [M]⁺ 740 (FABMS), has been isolated from ethanolic extract of the leaves of *Cassia sophera* Linn. along with a known compound **2**, 8-prenyl-3,7,4'-trihydroxy-5-methoxyflavone. Compound **1** was characterized as 3,7,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone-5-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→4)-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside by several colour reactions, spectral analysis and chemical degradations.

Keywords : *Cassia sophera* Linn., Leguminosae, flavonol glycoside, antimicrobial activity.

Cassia sophera Linn. belongs to family Leguminosae. It is commonly known as 'Kasundi' or 'Banar' in Hindi. It is a shrub or under shrub 2.4–3 m high, annual or perennial. It is distributed throughout India and in most tropical countries. Its bark, leaves and seeds are used as cathartic. Its leaves are used externally in ringworm. Its bark and seeds are useful in diabetes. Decoction of plant is used in acute bronchitis^{1,2}.

Earlier workers^{3,4} have reported the presence of various constituents from this plant. In the present paper we report the isolation and structural elucidation of new flavonol glycoside 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone-5-O-β-D-xylopyranosyl-(1→4)-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→4)-O-α-L-rhamnopyranoside (**1**) along with a known compound, 8-prenyl-3,7,4'-trihydroxy-5-methoxyflavone (**2**).

Results and discussion

The ethanolic extract of the leaves of this plant afforded a novel flavonol glycoside **1**, m.p. 282–284 °C, m.f. C₃₃H₄₀O₁₉ and [M]⁺ 740 (FABMS). It gave Molisch

and shinoda tests⁵, showing its flavonoid glycosidic nature. Its IR spectra showed absorption bands at 3450 (-OH), 3015 (-CH aromatic), 2952 (-CH saturated), 2865 (-OMe), 1647 (>C=O), 1620 (aromatic ring system), 1490, 1232, 1120 and 837 cm⁻¹. The bands in its UV spectrum at 270 and 352 nm showed its flavonoid skeleton. The bathochromic shift of 52 nm with AlCl₃ and 60 nm with NaOMe in band I revealed the presence of -OH group at C-3 and C-4' position in compound **1**⁶.

In ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **1**, two *meta* coupled doublets (*J* 2.1 Hz) at δ 6.35 and 6.78 were assigned to H-6 and H-8 protons⁷. Two signals at δ 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz) and 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz) were assigned to H-2', H-6' and H-3', H-5' in ring B, respectively⁷. The anomeric proton signals at δ 5.38 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 5.05 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz) and 5.10 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz) were assigned to H-1'', H-1''', H-1'''' of L-rhamnose, D-glucose and D-xylose, respectively. In ¹H NMR spectrum coupling constants of *J*_{1,2}, 7.1 Hz and 7.0 Hz for the anomeric protons of glucose and xylose, respectively, confirmed the β configurations of D-glucose and D-xylose, while

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small $J_{1,2}$ (1.5 Hz) value of anomeric proton of L-rhamnose, confirmed α configuration of L-rhamnose⁸. One singlet at δ 3.81 was assigned to -OMe group at C-7 position. The signal at δ 56.1 in ^{13}C NMR spectra, further confirmed the presence of -OMe group at C-7 position. Characteristic ions appeared at m/z 608 [$\text{M}^+ - 132$], 446 [$\text{M}^+ - 132 - 162$], 300 [$\text{M}^+ - 132 - 162 - 146$], were obtained by subsequent loss from the molecular ion of D-xylose, D-glucose and L-rhamnose units, suggesting D-xylose as terminal sugar, D-glucose as a middle sugar and L-rhamnose was linked to aglycone.

Acid hydrolysis of compound **1** with 10% ethanolic H_2SO_4 gave aglycone **3**, m.p. 221–223 °C, m.f. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$, [M]⁺ 300 (FABMS), which was identified as 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone by comparison of its spectral data (UV, IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) with literature values^{9–11}.

The aqueous hydrolysate, after the removal of aglycone, was neutralized with BaCO_3 and BaSO_4 filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography¹² using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent. Sugars were identified as D-glucose (R_f 0.19), D-xylose (R_f 0.25) and L-rhamnose (R_f 0.35) (by Co-PC).

Quantitative estimation of sugars according to the procedure of Mishra and Rao¹³, revealed that all the three sugars were present in equimolar ratio (1 : 1 : 1). Periodate oxidation of compound **1**, confirmed that all the sugars were present in the pyranose form¹⁴.

The relative locations of the sugar moieties in compound **1** were determined by permethylation¹⁵ followed by acid hydrolysis which yielded methylated sugars and methylated aglycone. The methylated sugars were identified as 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-xylose (by Co-PC). The methylated aglycone m.f. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$, m.p. 209–210°C, [M]⁺ 328 (FABMS), identified as 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone (see Experimental section). It showed that C-1''' of D-xylose linked with C-4''' of D-glucose, C-1''' of D-glucose attached with C-4'' of L-rhamnose and C-1'' of L-rhamnose was linked with C-5 position of the aglycone¹⁶. Glycosylation at C-5 position was further confirmed by comparing the ^{13}C NMR spectral data of compound **1** and aglycone **3**, in which an upfield shift of 1.8 ppm for C-5 signal and downfield shifts of 0.9, 1.2 and 1.8 ppm were attributed for *ortho* related C-6 and C-10 and *para* related C-8 signals, respectively¹⁷. The absence of glycosidation shift in ^{13}C NMR spectra of xylose, suggested that xylose was terminal sugar. The

downfield shift at δ 80.0 for C-4'' and at δ 74.8 for C-4''' in ^{13}C NMR spectrum, confirmed that interglycosidic linkages (1→4) were found between D-xylose and D-glucose, as well as D-glucose and L-rhamnose (see Experimental section).

Enzymatic hydrolysis of **1** with almond emulsin liberated D-xylose (R_f 0.25) first followed by D-glucose (R_f 0.19) and afforded a proaglycone 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone-5-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranoside, showed the presence of β -linkage between D-xylose and D-glucose, as well as D-glucose and proaglycone. Proaglycone on further hydrolysis with takadiastase liberated L-rhamnose (R_f 0.35) and aglycone, confirmed the presence of α -linkage between L-rhamnose and aglycone.

On the basis of the above evidences, the structure of compound **1** was characterized as 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone-5-*O*- β -D-xylopyranosyl-(1→4)-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1→4)-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranoside.

Compound **2** was analysed for molecular formula $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_6$, m.p. 274–276 °C, [M^+] 368 (FABMS), found (%) : C 68.43, H 5.18; calcd. (%) for m.f. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_6$: C 68.48, H 5.16. It was identified as 8-prenyl-3,7,4'-trihydroxy-5-methoxyflavone by comparison of its spectral data (UV, IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, MS) with the literature values¹⁸.

Compound **1** was tested for antibacterial and antifungal activity against various bacteria and fungi. The results given in Table 1, showed a wide variation of antibacterial and antifungal activity. The antibacterial activity of compound **1** was found to be fairly good against gram negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and gram positive bacteria *Bacillus coagulans*. Compound **1** also showed high antifungal activity against *Trichoderma viride* and *Fusarium oxysporium* even on very dilute concentration. Therefore it was cleared that compound **1** may potentially be used as therapeutic agent diseases caused by these microorganism.

Experimental

General experimental procedure :

All of the melting points were determined by Thiele apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer in KBr pellets; ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz using solvent CDCl_3 and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at 90 MHz using solvent $\text{DMSO}-d_6$; UV spectra were recorded on UV/Vis Perkin-Elmer Lambda 15 spectrometer and mass spectra on Jeol SX-102 (FAB) Mass spectrometer.

Plant material :

The leaves of *Cassia sophera* were procured from M/s United Chemicals and Allied Products, Kolkata and were taxonomically authenticated by the Taxonomist, Dr. A. S. Mishra, Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India. A voucher specimen has been deposited in the Natural Products Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India.

Extraction and isolation :

Air dried powdered leaves (2 kg) of the plant were extracted with 95% ethanol in a Soxhlet apparatus for 10 h. The ethanolic extract of the leaves was further exhaustively partitioned with pet. ether (40–60 °C), benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The ethyl acetate soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield brown viscous mass. It showed two spots on TLC examination using solvent system CHCl₃ : MeOH : H₂O (10 : 6 : 4), indicating it to be a mixture of **1** and **2**. These compounds were separated by column chromatography over silica gel, and purified by preparative TLC and studied separately.

Study of compound 1 :

Compound **1** was recrystallized from methanol as light yellow needles. It had m.p. 282–284 °C, m.f. C₃₃H₁₄O₁₅. [M]⁺ 740 (FABMS); found (%) : C 53.48, H 5.38, calcd. (%) for m.f. C₃₃H₁₄O₁₅ : C 53.51, H 5.40; UV (MeOH) λ_{max} (nm) : 260, 350; (+AlCl₃) 272, 305(sh) 345(sh), 402; (+AlCl₃-HCl) 271, 307(sh), 345(sh), 402; (+NaOCH₃), 262, 410; (+NaOAc) 262, 354, 218; (+NaOAc-H₃BO₃) 220, 262, 355; IR ν_{max} (KBr) (cm⁻¹): 3450 (-OH), 3015 (-CH aromatic), 2952 (-CH saturated), 2865 (-OMe), 1647 (>C=O), 1620 (aromatic ring system), 1490, 1252, 1120, 837 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-6), 3.81 (3H, s, OMe-7), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.9 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.38 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-1''), 1.18 (3H, d, *J* 6.7 Hz, Me-6''), 5.10 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz, H-1'''), 5.05 (1H, d, *J* 7.0, H-1''''), 3.95–4.60 (18H, m, sugar protons); ¹³C NMR (90 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 156.3 (C-2), 133.0 (C-3), 177.8 (C-4), 159.4 (C-5), 98.9 (C-6), 165.6 (C-7), 99.9 (C-8), 155.0 (C-9), 107.1 (C-10), 120.7 (C-1'), 112.0 (C-2'), 115.4 (C-3'), 147.2 (C-4'), 114.9 (C-5'), 122.9 (C-6'), 102.1 (C-1''), 77.2 (C-2''), 72.0 (C-3''), 80.0 (C-4''), 72.5 (C-5''), 18.5 (C-6''), 100.8 (C-1'''), 84.1 (C-2'''), 76.9 (C-3'''), 74.8 (C-4'''), 76.1 (C-5'''), 61.2 (C-6'''), 99.8 (C-1''''), 74.0 (C-2''''), 76.0 (C-3''''), 72.0 (C-4''''), 67.0 (C-5''''), 56.1 (OMe-7). MS

(FABMS) *m/z* 740 [M]⁺, 608 [M⁺-xylose], 446 [M⁺-xylose-glucose], 300 [aglycone]⁺.

Acid hydrolysis of compound 1 :

100 mg of compound **1** was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed with 15 ml of 10% H₂SO₄ on water bath for 8 h. The contents were concentrated and allowed to cool and residue was extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel using CHCl₃ : MeOH (7 : 3) to give compound **3**, which was identified as 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone by comparison with its known spectral referred data. The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralized with BaCO₃ and the BaSO₄ filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent. Sugars were identified as D-glucose (*R*_f 0.19), D-xylose (*R*_f 0.25) and L-rhamnose (*R*_f 0.35).

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Study of compound 3 :

It had m.f. C₁₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 221–223 °C, [M]⁺ 300 (FABMS); found (%) : C 63.92, H 4.08, calcd. (%) : C 64.0, H 4.00; UV λ_{max}(nm) : 260, 352; (+AlCl₃) 270, 301(sh), 347(sh), 400; (+AlCl₃-HCl) 270, 302(sh), 345(sh), 400; (+NaOMe) 265, 397; (+NaOAc) 218, 260, 345; (+NaOAc-H₃BO₃) 218, 260, 356; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3452, 3010, 2945, 2865, 1650, 1622, 1498, 835; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 6.32 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-6), 3.80 (3H, s, OMe-7), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.87 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'); ¹³C NMR (90 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm) : 138.4 (C-2), 134.1 (C-3), 178.0 (C-4), 161.2 (C-5), 98.0 (C-6), 165.8 (C-7), 98.3 (C-8), 156.1 (C-9), 106.0 (C-10), 121.5 (C-1'), 113.0 (C-2'), 115.0 (C-3'), 148.0 (C-4'), 115.0 (C-5'), 130.3 (C-6'), 57.2 (OMe-7).

Permethylolation of compound 1 :

Compound **1** (150 mg) was refluxed with MeI (5 ml) and Ag₂O (35 ml) in DMF (5.0 mg) for one day and then filtered. The filtrate was hydrolysed with 10% ethanolic H₂SO₄ for 8 h to give the methylated aglycone **4**, identified as 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxy flavone and methylated

sugars which were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-xylose, 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose (Co-PC).

Study of compound 4 :

It had m.f. C₁₈H₁₆O₆, m.p. 209–210 °C, [M]⁺ 328 (FABMS); found (%) : C 65.81, H 4.87, calcd. (%) : C 65.85, H 4.89; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3450, 3013, 2940, 2864, 1650, 1621, 1497, 832; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) : 3.89 (3H, s, OMe-3), 6.30 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-6), 3.81 (3H, s, OMe-7), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.90 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.00 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3',5').

Enzymatic hydrolysis of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (20 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (25 ml) and hydrolysed with an equal volume of almond emulsin. The reaction mixture was allowed to stay at room temperature for two days and filtered. The proaglycone and hydrolysate were studied separately.

The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent, which showed the presence of D-xylose (*R*_f 0.25) and D-glucose (*R*_f 0.19) (Co-PC).

The proaglycone was dissolved in MeOH (20 ml) and hydrolysed with an equal volume of takadiastase at room temperature as usual procedure yielded aglycone, identified as 3,5,4'-trihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone and sugar was identified as L-rhamnose (*R*_f 0.35) (Co-PC).

Antimicrobial activity of the compound 1 :

The antibacterial activity of the compound 1 was carried out by Filter Paper Disc Diffusion method¹⁹. The stock solution of the compound 1 was prepared of 1000 ppm in methanol, taken at different concentrations. For antibacterial activity, the sterile filter paper disc (6 mm) soaked with the standard antibacterial agent with various test samples of compound 1 was placed on the seeded agar plates and were kept in incubator at 36 ± 1 °C for 36 h. The diameters of zone of inhibition were measured.

For the antifungal activity of compound 1, Saboraud's²⁰ broth media with 4% agar was used for the preparation of plates and inoculated with the spore and mycelium suspension of fungi, obtained from 7 days old culture. The plates after inoculation were incubated at room temperature for 48 h and the zone of inhibition are reported in the Table 1.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of the compound 1

Sl. no.	Bacterial species	Diameters of zone of inhibition (mm) ^a				Std. ^b
		Concentration of compound 1 (%)				
		100	80	60	40	
1. (+)	<i>Bacillus coagulans</i>	16.8	12.8	9.0	5.1	21.2
2. (+)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	9.6	6.2	3.0	–	20.0
3. (–)	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	8.8	7.0	3.1	–	18.3
4. (–)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	19.4	16.1	13.2	9.7	23.1
	Fungal species					Std. ^c
1.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	6.7	3.4	1.6	–	16.8
2.	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	18.9	14.7	10.0	7.2	23.4
3.	<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>	17.9	13.1	9.7	6.0	22.1
4.	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	8.3	4.3	2.0	–	23.7

^aThe zone of inhibition (mm) taken as average of four determination direction.

^bStreptomycin (1000 ppm) used as standard antibacterial agent.

^cGriseofulvin (1000 ppm) used as standard antifungal agent.

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